

*Human Defiance and the Name of God—
an Analysis of Goliath's Speech and David's Speech*

1 Samuel 17:10, 37

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

ABSTRACT

This essay examines the literary and rhetorical function of two speech pauses in 1 Samuel 17. The first occurred in Goliath's taunt. It is a pause that intensified fear, exposing Israel's paralysis before a grotesquely human conception of power. The second pause occurred in David's address to Saul ahead of the first use of the divine name in the story, shifting the perspective from human strength to divine deliverance. Through attention to repetition, pronouns, verbal forms, pauses and structural symmetry, the essay argues that these silences heighten dramatic tension while contrasting human perception with faith in Jehovah, to whom the battle ultimately belonged.*

1 Samuel 17:10

וַיֹּאמֶר הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי אֲנִי חִרְפְּתִי אֶת־מַעְרְכֹת יִשְׂרָאֵל הַיּוֹם הַזֶּה תִּגְדֹּלִי אִישׁ וְנִלְחָמָה יַחַד

Descriptions of appearance are rare in the Bible. When Goliath stepped out into the open as אִישׁ־הַבְּיָנִים , “a man of the in-betweens”, someone willing to stand in the open between the armies, we are given *four* verses detailing his appearance. The details focus on his height and his armour (verses 4–7). His portrayal tells us that he looks invincible from a human perspective. This viewpoint is important because this chapter is about the human outlook versus the divine outlook. When we are told that the Israelites “became terrified and were greatly afraid” (verse 11) we know their perspective. Alter (p. 81) says that the description of Goliath is grotesquely quantitative embodiment of a hero, a mechanical conception of what constitutes power. It is an allegory of the human idea of power.

Following the comprehensive list of armour comes Goliath's lengthy הַרְפָּה, “taunt” (cf. verse 26), his challenge to Israel:

* See Appendix, page 9.

8 Why do YOU come out to draw up in battle formation? Am I not the Philistine and YOU servants belonging to Saul? Choose a man for yourselves, and let him come down to me. 9 If he is able to fight with me and he does strike me down, we must then become servants to YOU. But if I myself am a match for him and I do strike him down, YOU must also become servants to us, and YOU must serve us.

Then comes the pause.

I myself do taunt the battle lines of Israel this day. Give me a man, and let us fight together!

Why indeed did Israel “come out to draw up in battle formation”? They were in formation, but as Goliath could see, they did not seem to want a battle.

Then he contrasts his singular power with the entire army of Saul. Here he was a single Philistine against the servants of Saul. “Am I not the Philistine?” (verse 8), which implies he was known and feared everywhere. The speech is replete with the first person singular pronoun. Fokkelman (p. 150) notes a triple “I”. Conspicuous amongst these is that one in verse 8: הָלוֹא אֲנִי הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי, and the shortened form אֲנִי after the pause in verse 10. Implied in his pugnacious reproach in verse 8 was his freedom in contrast with the servants of Saul.

It has been noted that Saul “was taller than all the other people from his shoulders upward” (1 Samuel 10:23). He should have been the one who went out to Goliath. God has the power, but because of the challenge to his right to rule, he needs the agency of a willing human.

As Fokkelman points out, Goliath symmetrically says, “If he is able to fight with me and he does strike me down, we must then become servants to YOU. But if I myself am a match for him and I do strike him down, YOU must also become servants to us”, but adds at the end “and YOU must serve us”, making a triple mention of slavery. The last of which is slavery not just as a description but as an activity. It was after this picture of life if Israel failed, that Goliath paused.

His pause allowed for a response—a champion to face him. The absence of such a response—the silence from the ‘battle lines of Israel’—exposed Israel’s impotence and increased the terror.

And the narrator used the pause to build tension and contrast.

We are not told how long the pause was. If it was long then the tension would have swollen in the silence.

When Goliath broke the silence he said with brio, אָנִי חִרְפֹּתִי אֶת־מַעְרְכֹת יִשְׂרָאֵל הַיּוֹם הַזֶּה, תִּנְגְּדֵנִי אִישׁ וְנִלְחַמָּה יַחַד, “I myself do taunt the battle lines of Israel this day. Give me a man, and let us fight together!”. Goliath’s use of the double pronoun אָנִי חִרְפֹּתִי, was no doubt meant to focus Israel’s attention on his sizeable and intimidating presence. After Israel’s non-response, his taunting garnered extra muscle. His concluding words were a compact, punchy summary of the opening lines. His first imperative had been in verse 8: בְּרֹדְלְכֶם אִישׁ, “Choose a man for yourselves!”; his second imperative is after the pause and it intensified his first: תִּנְגְּדֵנִי אִישׁ, “Give me a man!”—give him over now! He has gone from “choose!” to “give!”; from לְכֶם, “for yourselves”, to לִי, “for me”. It feels as if the progression is voracious.

These concluding words act as a “coup de grâce in the psychological warfare”, a “verbal defiance and bragging” (*ibid.*).

Goliath’s opinion of Israel was then confirmed as he saw their physical response: “When Saul and all Israel heard these words of the Philistine, then they became terrified and were greatly afraid” (verse 11).

All the while, in the background is the “living God” (verses 26 and 35) and Jehovah’s words to Samuel: “For how long will you be mourning for Saul, while I, on the other hand, have rejected him from ruling as king over Israel? Fill your horn with oil and go. I shall send you to Jesse the Bethlehemite, because I have provided among his sons a king for myself” (16:1).

1 Samuel 17:37

וַיֹּאמֶר דָּוִד וַיהוָה אֲשֶׁר הִצִּילֵנִי מִיַּד הָאֲרִי וּמִיַּד הַדָּב הוּא יִצִּילֵנִי מִיַּד הַפִּלִּשְׁתִּי הַזֶּה וַיֹּאמֶר שָׂאוּל אֶל־דָּוִד לֵךְ וַיהוָה יִהְיֶה עִמָּךְ

Having heard Goliath’s taunts and having told sufficient people that he would fight the giant, David was brought to Saul. He was so fervent and urgent that he did not wait for formalities or for the king to speak or to invite him to speak, instead without a prompt he launched into his proposal (verse 32):

Do not let the heart of any man collapse within him. Your servant himself will go and actually fight with this Philistine.

David’s confidence and eagerness in front of the king was exhilarating. His opening words were full of determination and he was not far off issuing a proscriptive command to the king. His trust in Jehovah had made him daring. The nw

translation of *פָּלַ*, “collapse”, is just right—the root literally meaning to “fall”. David pictured the entire Israelite army already ‘fallen’ on the battlefield in the face of the Philistine’s challenge.

Of course, it should have been the other way round. Let us picture David, a young man, concerned about the threats of the Philistine, had gone to the king to tell him his worries, and then the king reassured the young man, ‘Do not let your heart collapse within you. Your king himself will go and actually fight with this Philistine’. That’s the way it should have been.

After his opening declaration, David then showed his deference, starting his next statement with *עַבְדְּךָ*, “your servant”. And because David had switched from the usual order of verb/subject to subject/verb in this instant, the NW has added “himself” to show the emphasis and focus David wanted to communicate to his king. The other reassurance that David seemed to want to convey was done through his use of the imperfect—going *יֵלֵךְ*, in contrast with the perfect for his fight *יִלָּחֶם*. *Insight* (vol. 1, p. 1075) tells us:

The condition of the action, rather than the time involved, is the important thing. The action is viewed as either complete or incomplete.

If the verb portrays completed action, it is in the perfect state.

In other words, David was telling Saul: the fight is already over, the result is inevitable, it is a foregone conclusion.

His last few words *עִם־הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי הַזֶּה*, “with this Philistine”, sound disdainful. Had it been just *עִם־הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי*, “with the Philistine”, it would not have had such a derisory tone. In fact, David used this phrase five times in the story (verses 26 (twice), 32, 36 and 37). The second time in verse 26 he used the rare synonym of *הַזֶּה*, namely *הַלְזֵי*. He even increased his scorn using the phrase *הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי הָעֵרֶל הַזֶּה*, “this uncircumcised Philistine” twice (verses 26 and 36). The Philistine is stripped of all the lengthy description in verses 4 to 7 and is reduced to “this Philistine”.

Saul’s first words were a layered objection (verse 33):

לֹא תוּכַל לָלֶכֶת אֶל־הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי הַזֶּה לְהִלָּחֵם עִמּוֹ כִּי־נֶעַר אַתָּה וְהוּא אִישׁ מִלְחָמָה מִנְעָרָיו

You are not able to go against this Philistine to fight with him, for you are but a boy, and he is a man of war from his boyhood.

Saul picked up on David’s dismissiveness and used it against him: *הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי הַזֶּה*. In the end, as we know, David did *לָלֶכֶת אֶל־הַפְּלִשְׁתִּי הַזֶּה*, *אֶל*, “to” this Philistine, but he

did not לְהִלָּחֵם עִמּוֹ, fight *with* him, which implies a struggle, which was presumably how Saul was imagining how the contest would unfold.

Saul described David as a נַעַר, which has a wide range of meanings from a baby (Exodus 2:6) to a servant of any age (2 Samuel 16:1). However, Saul was comparing David to Goliath who had been a אִישׁ מִלְחָמָה since being a נַעַר. Saul was saying that David had not even started, he was still at the point where Goliath had begun his career in war as a youth. Oddly enough, in 1 Samuel 16:18 David had been introduced to Saul as a אִישׁ מִלְחָמָה, “a man of war”. Perhaps Saul’s servant was overdoing David’s credentials or perhaps Saul was focused on appearances.

Saul now thought that Goliath and David were the obstacles, but ironically the obstacle was Saul.

David now countered this perceived experience gap with his next speech—the longest speech in the story. It will include a pause.

“34 Your servant became a shepherd of his father among the flock, and there came a lion, and also a bear, and [each] carried off a sheep from the drove. 35 And I went out after it and struck it down and made the rescue from its mouth. When it began rising against me, I grabbed hold of its beard and struck it down and put it to death. 36 Both the lion and the bear your servant struck down; and this uncircumcised Philistine must become like one of them, for he has taunted the battle lines of the living God. 37 Then David added: “Jehovah, who delivered me from the paw of the lion and from the paw of the bear, he it is who will deliver me from the hand of this Philistine.” At this Saul said to David: “Go, and may Jehovah himself prove to be with you.”

He started as a shepherd of his father’s flock, but this idyll was broken when both a lion and a bear carried away a sheep. His reaction was swift. When he caught up with the beasts the sheep were still alive! When the lion and the bear rose up against him, David killed them. Then the deduction: this uncircumcised Philistine must become like the lion and the bear that I struck down and killed. Goliath had put himself forward as אִישׁ-הַבֵּינַיִם, “a man-of-the-inbetweens”, a unique individual, set apart. Fokkelman notes that David now categorises Goliath amongst the wild animals that had come against the flock of his father, and in the case of Goliath, against the flock of the great shepherd Jehovah, his heavenly Father. A broad and emphatic nominality points always to God (p. 173).

Why would the Philistine die? “He has taunted the battle lines of the living God”. Ceresko (p. 66) used this passage to counter text-critical judgements, showing that the phrase, “Then David added” is central and thus not to be deleted “as a later expansion” as some translations have done (NEB, NIV, NLT, GNB). An important feature of this unit is its concentric structure around the pause.

“the lion” ... “the bear” (17:36a)
“this uncircumcised Philistine” (17:36b)
“the Living God” (17:36c)
“David” (17:37a)
“Yahweh” (17:37b)
“the lion” ... “the bear” (17:37c)
“this Philistine” (17:37d)

Ceresko said that David is surrounded by his enemies, but closer to him as a shield is his living God, Jehovah.

Why did David pause? Was he waiting for Saul to come up with another objection? Was he waiting for delighted approval? Was he waiting so that Saul could reflect on his conviction that as Jehovah had helped him kill a lion and a bear, so he will help him kill the Philistine? Was it a pause for emphasis, for dramatic effect?

After the pause David said: יהוה אֲשֶׁר הִצַּלְנִי מִיַּד הָאֲרִי וּמִיַּד הַדָּב הוּא יִצִּילֵנִי מִיַּד הַפִּלִּשְׁתִּי הַזֶּה.

His first word after the pause was the divine name—the first use of the name in this story. It was as if the narrator was reserving this potent name for David to use at the climax of his address to the king. Once said, the king used the name in submission to David’s faith, then David used it four times in his speech to Goliath. David countered his lack of experience by telling Saul that his qualifications are irrelevant, because לַיהוָה הַמְלָחָמָה, “to Jehovah belongs the battle” (verse 47).

Perhaps it is this use of the name straight after his pause that hints at the motive for the pause—a pause for emphasis and dramatic effect. In our consideration of the pause in Genesis 9:17 we proposed that the silence was used in the same way that a fermata is used at the conclusion of a piece of music—a moment of silence that creates dramatic tension and anticipation for the final resounding resolution. This would seem to be the intention of the pause. It is situated at just the right moment in a carefully crafted piece of persuasive rhetoric with plenty of drama and probably delivered with some pertinacious gusto. Such a speech would usually

use emotional appeal engaging the audience's feelings with vivid imagery, story telling and evocative language. It would also use logical deductions that would then confirm the credentials of the speaker. Stylistically, the speaker could use repetition, parallelism, metaphors and dramatic pauses. David used all these.

The king could only submit and say: "Go, and may Jehovah himself prove to be with you".

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alter. Robert Alter, *The Art of Biblical Narrative*, Basic Books, 1981.
- Ceresko Anthony R. Ceresko, “A Rhetorical Analysis of David’s ‘Boast’ (1 Samuel 17:34-37): Some Reflections on Method”, *Catholic Biblical Quarterly* 47.1 (Jan. 1985): 58-74.
- Fokkelman. J.P. Fokkelman, *Narrative Art and Poetry in the Books of Samuel, The Crossing Fates*, Volume II, Van Gorcum, 1986.
- GNB *Good News Bible, Today’s English Version*, The Bible Societies, Collins/Fontana, 1976.
- Insight*. *Insight on the Scriptures*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 2018.
- NEB *The New English Bible*, Oxford University Press, Cambridge University Press, 1970.
- NIV *Holy Bible, New International Version*, Hodder and Stoughton, 1980.
- NLT. *New Living Translation*, Tyndale House Foundation, 2015.
- NW *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 1984.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵי does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.